

Potential Local Anaesthetics Part-VIII.

Synthesis of Diethylamino-Morpholino-Piperidino-N-(β/ν -aryloxyalkyl)-acetamides.

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Some basic amides have been prepared by condensing substituted β - γ -aryloxyalkylamines with chloroacetyl-chloride and then replacing the halogen of the amides with secondary amines.

TRIVEDI and co-workers¹ synthesized basic amides from a variety of aralkylamines which exhibited significant local anaesthetic activity. As aryloxyalkylamines were also proved to exhibit local anaesthetic activity along with other pronounced pharmacological activities²⁻⁶, it was of considerable interest to prepare basic amides from aryloxyalkylamines. This communication reports the preparation of number of basic amides from β -aryloxyethyl and γ -aryloxypropylamines.

The compounds with asterisk in the tables showed significant activity when tested for surface anaesthesia⁷.

Experimental

β -Aryloxyethyl bromides and γ -aryloxypropyl bromides were prepared as described in literature⁸.

The required β/γ -aryloxyalkylamines were prepared from β/γ -aryloxyalkyl bromides by Delapine reaction⁹, as under.

β/γ -Aryloxyalkylamines: β/γ -Aryloxyalkyl bromide (1 mole) in chloroform was reacted with hexamethylene tetramine (1.1 mole) in chloroform and the mixture kept overnight. The solid obtained was heated with methanolic hydrochloric acid for 4-6 hr. After removing excess alcohol the amine hydrochloride was steamed to remove volatile impurities. After addition of excess ammonia the liberated base was extracted with ether and purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Yield was about 30-40%. Amines not reported so far are shown in table 1.

Condensation of chloroacetyl chloride with amines :

Chloroacetyl chloride (2.0 parts) was reacted with β/γ -aryloxyalkylamine (1.5 parts) in presence of acetone (2.5 parts) sodium acetate (2.0 parts) and water (3.0 parts) at ice temperature. After diluting the reaction mixture with water, the precipitate formed was washed with water, sodium carbonate solution (10%) and water. If the amide

was a liquid it was taken up in ether and purified by distillation under reduced pressure.

Condensation of secondary amines with α -chloro-N-aryloxy alkyl-acetamides¹⁰ :

A mixture of α -chloro-N-aryloxyalkyl acetamide (1.0 mole) and secondary amine (2.6 moles) in dry benzene (500 ml) was refluxed for six hours. The benzene solution after filtration was treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) and the aqueous extract was treated in cold with excess of ammonia to liberate the base. The solid base was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from petroleum ether and alcohol.

If the base liberated as an oil, it was extracted with ether, dried and converted into the hydrochloride by passing dry hydrogen chloride gas into its dry ethereal solution. The hydrochlorides were crystallised in needles from dry acetone. In some cases picrates and oxalates were prepared. Compounds prepared are shown in tables 2-5.

TABLE I. γ -ARYLOXYPROPYLAMINES

No.	X	B.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	<i>o</i> -Cl	130-132/6 mm	C ₉ H ₁₂ ONCl	7.40	7.60
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl	134-136/6 mm	C ₉ H ₁₂ ONCl	7.50	7.60
3.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	150/14 mm	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ ON	8.40	8.50
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	120-122/6 mm	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ ON	8.40	8.50
5.	2,4-Cl ₂	155-158/6-7 mm	C ₉ H ₁₁ ONCl ₂	6.50	6.40
6.	2,5-Cl ₂	185-187/16-18 mm	C ₉ H ₁₁ ONCl ₂	6.30	6.40
7.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	160-165/15 mm	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ ON	7.60	7.80
8.	2,CH ₃ -4-Cl	145-150/7 mm	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONCl	6.90	7.00
9.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	155-160/6-7 mm	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONCl	6.80	7.00

TABLE 2. α -CHLORO-N-ARYLOXYALKYL ACETAMIDES :

No.	n	X	M.P. degree °C	B.P. degree °C	Molecular formula	Percent Chlorine		Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required	Found	Required
1.	2	<i>o</i> -Cl	Oil	—	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	..	..	...	5.60
2.	2	<i>p</i> -Cl	87-88	—	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	28.70	28.60	5.60	6.20
3.	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	56	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl	15.60	15.60	6.10	6.20
4.	2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	74	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl	15.70	15.60	6.20	6.20
5.	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	79	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl	15.70	15.60	6.30	5.00
6.	2	2,5-(Cl) ₂	89	—	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl ₃	37.70	37.70	5.10	5.80
7.	2	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	69	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	14.80	14.70	5.80	5.80
8.	2	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	84	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	14.70	14.70	5.90	5.30
9.	2	2-(CH ₃ -4-Cl)	84	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂	27.20	27.10	5.30	6.10
10.	3	H	—	155-160/8 mm.	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl	15.40	15.60	5.90	5.30
11.	3	<i>o</i> -Cl	60-62	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ NCl ₂	27.10	27.10	5.10	5.30
12.	3	<i>p</i> -Cl	68-70	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ NCl ₂	27.20	27.10	5.50	5.70
13.	3	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	—	160-165/12-14 mm.	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	14.50	14.70	5.50	5.70
14.	3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	71	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	14.70	14.70	5.70	4.70
15.	3	2,4-(Cl) ₂	88	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl ₃	35.80	35.90	4.60	4.70
16.	3	2,5-(Cl) ₂	72-75	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl ₃	35.70	35.90	4.60	5.50
17.	3	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	70-71	—	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ NCl	13.70	13.90	5.30	5.10
18.	3	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	92-93	—	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl ₂	25.50	25.70	4.90	5.10
19.	3	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	—	175-185/10 mm.	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂	25.90	25.70	5.00	5.10

TABLE 3

No.	n	X	A	M.P. degree °C	Molecular Formula	Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required
1.	2	<i>o</i> -Cl	HCl	103	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.70	8.70
2.	2	<i>p</i> -Cl	Picrate	132	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.80	13.60
3.	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	Picrate	140	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	14.10	14.20
4.	2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	Picrate	132	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	14.00	14.20
5.	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	69	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	9.20	9.30
6.	2	2,5-(Cl) ₂	Picrate	164	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	12.90	12.80
7.	2	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Picrate	142	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.80	13.80
8.	2	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	HCl	114	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.90	8.90
9.	2	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	Picrate	108-110	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.40	13.30
10.	3	H	HCl	80-81	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	9.30	9.30
11.*	3	<i>o</i> -Cl	HCl	100-102	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.20	8.40
12.*	3	<i>p</i> -Cl	HCl	104-105	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.30	8.40
13.	3	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	HCl	90-92	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.80	8.90
14.*	3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	98-100	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	9.00	8.90
15.*	3	2,4-(Cl) ₂	HCl	98-100	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.50	7.60
16.	3	2,5-(Cl) ₂	Oxalate	125-128	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.40	6.60
17.	3	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	HCl	98-99	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.60	8.50
18.	3	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	Oxalate	105-107	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.90	7.00
19.	3	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	Oxalate	120-122	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.80	7.00

TABLE 4

No.	n	X	A	M.P. degree °C	Molecular formula	Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required
1.	2	<i>o</i> -Cl	HCl	87	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.30	8.40
2.	2	<i>p</i> -Cl	HCl	158	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.40	8.40
3.	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	HCl	89	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	9.00	8.90
4.	2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	HCl	159	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.80	8.90
5.	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	166	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.80	8.90
6.	2	2,5-(Cl) ₂	HCl	187	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.40	7.60
7.	2	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	HCl	157	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.50	8.50
8.	2	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	HCl	102	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.40	8.50
9.	2	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	...	99	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	9.10	9.00
10.	3	H	HCl	140-141	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.90	8.90
11.	3	<i>o</i> -Cl	HCl	130-131	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.10	8.00
12.*	3	<i>p</i> -Cl	HCl	150-151	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.HCl	7.90	8.00
13.	3	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	HCl	139-140	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.40	8.50
14.	3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	136-139	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.50	8.50
15.	3	2,4-(Cl) ₂	HCl	126-128	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.HCl	7.20	7.30
16.	3	2,5-(Cl) ₂	HCl	139-141	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.20	7.30
17.*	3	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	HCl	114-115	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ .HCl	8.10	8.20
18.	3	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	Oxalate	136-139	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.50	6.70
19.	3	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	HCl	126-128	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl.HCl	7.50	7.70

TABLE 5

No.	n	X	A	M.P. degree °C	Molecular formula	Percent Nitrogen	
						Found	Required
1.	2	<i>o</i> -Cl	...	66-67	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.50	9.50
2.	2	<i>p</i> -Cl	HCl	197	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.30	8.40
3.	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	...	62	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂	10.10	10.20
4.	2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	HCl	103	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	9.10	9.00
5.*	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	113	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.90	9.00
6.	2	2,5-(Cl) ₂	HCl	162	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.60	7.60
7.	2	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Picrate	128	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .C ₆ H ₂ (NO ₂) ₃ OH	13.40	13.50
8.	2	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	HCl	69	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.40	8.60
9.	2	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	...	94	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.10	9.00
10.	3	H	HCl	99-101	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.90	9.00
11.	3	<i>o</i> -Cl	HCl	76-78	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.00	8.10
12.	3	<i>p</i> -Cl	Oxalate	137-139	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.80	7.00
13.	3	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	HCl	84-85	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.40	8.60
14.*	3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	HCl	104-106	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.50	8.60
15.	3	2,4-(Cl) ₂	Oxalate	142-145	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.20	6.40
16.	3	2,5-(Cl) ₂	Oxalate	154-156	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.20	6.40
17.	3	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	Oxalate	132-135	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ .H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	7.00	7.10
18.	3	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	Oxalate	132	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.60	6.80
19.	3	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	Oxalate	142-144	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.90	6.80

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